

SIGNIFICANCE OF INTEGRATED APPROACH TO LANGUAGE TEACHING IN MIXED-LEVEL CLASSES IN PHILOLOGICAL AND NON-PHILOLOGICAL FIELDS.

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Abstract

Teaching foreign languages to both philological and non-philological groups, requires the teacher to have special training, to work tirelessly on himself, to successfully conduct lessons using various methods and approaches. It will not be difficult for teachers with the right teaching style to work in such groups. Therefore, every teacher who wants to be perfect in working with such groups must choose methods and approaches that are suitable for such classes. In this article, we will discuss the advantages and disadvantages of mixed-ability classes and some pedagogical strategies that help in organizing the teaching process.

Key words: *Students, strategies, gap analysis, lesson planning, grouping, purposes, gamification, motivation, achievement*

Abstrakt

Bugungi kunda filologik va nofilologik guruhlar bilan ishlash o‘qituvchidan maxsus tayyorgarlikka ega bo‘lishni, o‘z ustida tinimsiz ishlashni, turli metod va yondashuvlardan foydalangan holda darsni muvaffaqiyatli o‘tkazishni talab etadi. To‘g‘ri o‘qitish uslubiga ega o‘qituvchilar uchun bunday guruhlarda ishlash qiyin bo‘lmaydi. Shuning uchun bunday guruhlar bilan ishlashda mukammal bo‘lishni istagan har bir o‘qituvchi bunday darslarga mos keladigan usul va yondashuvlarni tanlashi kerak. Ushbu maqolada bilim darajasi turlicha bo‘lgan guruhlarda ishlashning afzalliklari va qiyinchiliklari hamda o‘qitish jarayonini tashkil etishda yordam beruvchi ba’zi pedagogik strategiyalarni muhokama qilamiz.

Kalit so‘zlar: talabalar, yondashuv, bo‘shliqlarni tahlil qilish, darsni rejalashtirish, guruhlash, maqsadlar, o‘yinlashtirish, motivatsiya, yutuqlar

Аннотация

Сегодня работа с филологическими и нефилологическими группами требует от учителя специальной подготовки, неустанной работы над собой, успешного проведения урока с использованием различных методов и подходов. Учителям, обладающим правильными методами обучения, не составит труда работать в таких группах. Поэтому каждый учитель, желающий совершенствоваться в работе с такими группами, должен выбирать методы и подходы, подходящие для таких занятий. В этой статье мы обсудим преимущества и недостатки занятий смешанного обучения в нефилологических группах, а также некоторые педагогические стратегии, помогающие организовать учебный процесс.

Ключевые слова: учащиеся, стратегии, анализ пробелов, планирование урока, группировка, цели, геймификация, мотивация, достижение

In the process of teaching English to students over decades, language teachers have experienced several approaches, methods, and techniques and it is obvious that they have to learn from their strengths and weaknesses. From the Grammar-Translation Method, the Structural Approach, and the Communicative Approach, educators have gained insights how to help learners to acquire and utilize the target language. The long journey of language teaching and learning seems to be nearing its destination (David and Hunt, 2002).

However, in teaching language both philological and non-philological students, the issue of the lack of attention in class has always been a challenge for educators and professors. The main reason for this lack of attention is simply the students' lack of focus on learning and the gap in their knowledge or the failure of the education system to evolve with them. Working out how to plan for such a diverse classroom can be intimidating. In such groups, it can be difficult to give each student the attention they need. At this point, students may lose interest if they perceive the material as too difficult or not complicated, which can cause students to have trouble concentrating during class. All this leads to teacher fatigue and reduces the effectiveness of the learning process. Here, we can see the challenges of mixed level classes. They are;

- Determining appropriate teaching resources and material. Materials selected by the teacher may not be suitable for all students.
- Organizing appropriate groupings within the class. When dividing such classes into small groups, attention should be paid to the student's level of knowledge, and it is important to monitor the participation of each student.
- Identifying the individual needs of each student. Determining the gap in the student's knowledge and correctly approaching it is one of the important requirements of the teaching process.
- Ensuring that all learners are challenged and interested. In order to find or pick out activities that can equally interest the students in teaching process, the teacher has to search a lot.

However, if these classes are handled properly or if educators choose the right teaching methods, working with such students will not only make our lesson more effective, but it can also be beneficial to the teachers. For example;

- Students are able to learn at their own pace. Students can improve their knowledge with the help of the right direction given by the teacher.
- Students learn to work well in a group. When students work in groups, they should be taught that each group member's opinion and response should be taken into account, moreover, mutual collaboration should be developed.
- Students become independent learners. It is important to encourage students to become self-disciplined learners. Teachers should think of ways to support them in

making the commitment to begin achieving their goals and it makes learners to take responsibility for their own learning.

- Students develop strong relationships with their peers. Learners understand each other better in the process of interaction, and by correcting their shortcomings, they develop their knowledge. (T. Banwel, 2008)

- It is a great opportunity to develop teaching skills. By working on themselves during teaching process, educators develop lesson plans and teaching strategies that will keep students engaged and present, and will soon be able to create a positive learning environment for students without spending hours on planning.

- Students become partners in learning. The goal of these learning partnerships is to facilitate subject learning where partners knowingly support each other in achieving their learning goals. More specifically, partners in learning strives to encourage, promote, and engage each student in effective problem solving, reasoning, and other forms of higher-order thinking with their partners. (George, P. G. (1994).)

To achieve such necessary results, it is better to combine the advantages of traditional and modern methods to get a new teaching method. After all, an integrative approach in the teaching process is adequate and appropriate, and we guide students to learn information and materials from books, expand the knowledge fund, expand and strengthen the educational content using new innovations. Update teaching ideas and methods; it is necessary to combine advanced teaching methods with scientific teaching methods.

ICTs have become a crucial element in ELT both within the classroom and, more importantly, outside the classroom, where they provide the necessary tools and give full sense to the idea of learner autonomy. The advantages of ICT usage in foreign language teaching have been described by many educators. At the same time, they can be listed here:

Project-based learning. Project-based learning is all about encouraging students to actively participate through exploration and real-world problems. Creativity, perseverance and teamwork are also integral parts of project work. Through this method, it is possible to get students to work closely in a group.

Grouping strategies and purposes. By the help of flexible grouping teaching practice, teachers put students into temporary groups to work together for only as long as is needed for them to develop an identified skill or to complete a learning activity. The groups can be heterogeneous (group of varying skill levels) or homogeneous (group of the same skill level). The groups change often based on the learning objective and learners' needs or interests. (Mathew, 2013)

Task-Based Learning. Task-based learning (TBL) is also known as Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) and Task-Based Instruction (TBI). It focuses on meaningful tasks, such as creating a poster, producing a newsletter, video or pamphlet, and designing a class or group map.

Active learning. Learners share their views on strategies depend on different active learning methods, such as ICT use, collaborative learning and experiential learning, and their implications for teaching, assessment, curriculum design and higher education management. Active learning provides real-life problem-solving skills and prepares students to become responsible and active citizens.

Collaborative learning. A collaborative (or cooperative) learning approach involves students working together on activities or learning tasks in groups small enough to ensure that everyone participates. Group students can work on separate tasks that contribute to the overall result or work together on a common task.

Problem based learning. Problem-based learning requires learners to use their problem-solving skills to respond to a given situation. For example, they can be presented a scenario and asked to provide strategies or solutions. The task is assigned to either individuals or groups. They present with the findings they come up with in various forms, such as multimedia presentation, role-play, and written report. (Simonson, 2000.)

Conclusion. As mentioned above, different methods and approaches are important components of language teaching and learning. Without effective methods and clear strategies, it is impossible to know whether students have learned, whether teaching has been effective, or how best to meet students' learning needs. In the process of teaching foreign languages to philological and non-philological students, the integrative approach is deeply and strongly related to student activity. A suitable approach to teaching a foreign language in such groups gives students great opportunities to learn the language and demonstrate their abilities.

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